

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Stakeholders' views on the agricultural practices applied in potato crop in the Atlantic central area: obstacles and effective proposals

Identifying the most relevant current agri-environmental problems of potato crop and the priority needs of end-users is necessary to assess the practical potential for integrating more sustainable farming practices into the different farming systems. In the Atlantic central, 22 people responded to the survey in Jan-Feb 2020: potato farmers, researchers, agricultural technical advisors and other stakeholders (average age: 45.3 years). The most serious problems they identified were rainfall and linked irrigation water scarcity during growing period, high incidence of fungal diseases linked to a high use of plant protection products and development of resistances, and soil compaction. The respondents suggested that the highest priority should be given to increasing soil organic matter, improving soil structure, and increasing soil fertility. As potentially remedy soil problems,

the respondents stated the following practices would be equally effective under organic and conventional farming, but still more effective in a diversified cropping system: (i) minimum tillage, i.e. a reduced tillage frequency (although also quite a few thought none of the listed practices would be effective); (ii) adding solid organic manure or using green manure; (iii) using catch crops to reduce N/P-leaching (too few respondents commented on the high incidence of fungal diseases). According to their point of view, the main barrier that hinders the implementation of these practices is the lack of knowledge among farmers about their (cost) effectiveness of farming practices. Therefore, there is a need to research, advise and keep farmers informed in order to steer agriculture towards profitable and sustainable production systems.

1. Potato field with problems in the Atlantic Central region.

2. Healthy potato field in the Atlantic Central region.

KEYWORDS

Stakeholders' survey, potato production problems, sustainable farming practices

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